

BASES OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL SUPPORT OF THE PROCESS OF FORMATION OF SPECIAL TOURIST KNOWLEDGE, ABILITIES AND SKILLS

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Abstract. *In this article is opened the main content of sports tourism is overcoming the natural obstacles of the natural terrain. These obstacles are very diverse: rocks, snow, ice, water obstacles and many other types, types and forms of natural obstacles of the local macro- and microrelief. Sports and tourism qualities are developed and instructions for improvement are given.*

Keywords: *sports tourism, endurance, speed, strength of various muscle groups, agility, sports travel, extreme tourism, courtesy, responsibility, sensitivity, discipline, friendliness, tolerance, etiquette, large, submaximal and maximum cardiovascular walking.*

The main content of sports tourism is to overcome the natural obstacles of the local terrain. These obstacles are very diverse: rocks, snow, ice, water obstacles and many other types, types and forms of natural obstacles of local macro- and micro-relief. Sports tourism. develops and improves qualities. According to the types of movement, motor-motor tourism, bicycle, water, sailing, horse, ski, motorcycle, pedestrian, mountain, speleo-tourism, mixed types of tourism are distinguished. Depending on the social and age characteristics, sports tourism includes children's tourism, youth tourism, adult tourism, family tourism, tourism for the disabled. In recent years, the following directions of sports tourism have been actively developed: sports trips, extreme tourism, covering sports distances by types of tourism, in closed places on artificial terrain, on short routes in the class of sports trips. Natural conditions allow the teacher to more effectively influence the inner world of students, their value orientations, goal attitudes, and interpersonal relationships. In particular, in the conditions of tourist activities, the teacher is able to form the following personal qualities: politeness, responsibility, sensitivity, discipline, friendliness, tolerance, ethics, creative qualities.

As a means of improving the health of the population, tourist walks include many hours of moderate and low-intensity cyclic work related to long walks on trails with backpacks, climbing mountains, and traversing difficult terrain. Basically, average power works, although individual parts of it are located in the large, submaximal and maximal power zones.

The tourist training of future physical education bachelors includes the development of special motor qualities, general and special endurance, mastering the techniques and tactics of overcoming the route, teaching the methodology of planning the educational process, management of tourist activities, life support skills in extreme environments. The most important issues for quality training in the field of sports and health tourism are the organization, preparation and conduct of tourist trips, including food, equipment, organization of parking and accommodation in various conditions, personal self-development, etc.

Various forms of tourism allow it to be used as a means of physical education from preschool age. In pre-school and primary school age, walking with hygienic goals takes a big place.

In elementary school age, field trips are added with learning objectives. Walking with a load and a moderate load strengthens the cardiovascular system, and tourism helps to educate responsibility, tolerance and willpower.

In order to improve the quality of formation of professional competences in tourism, the main aspects of the organization of the educational process were identified and justified, the research used educational test technologies using non-verbal cartographic materials to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

In addition, it should be noted that the following types of training are traditionally included in the curriculum of sports and health tourism: general tourism, special tourism, physical and integral, and at the same time, the specific features of future work with preschool children include walking, physical education and sports. is to attract to tourism by promoting holidays, family tourism. Requirements for tourism activities in physical education classes include orientation elements, school tourism gatherings, familiarization with basic tourism technologies. Additional education has the goal of training elite athletes in tourism, as well as their participation in various high-level events; tourist equipment - purchase of equipment, creation of a material and technical base for the construction of sports-tourist polygons and simulators, and the conceptual basis of organizing a tourist trip consists of setting goals and tasks, recruiting a group, developing a route, preparing route documents. Therefore, the teacher must have high organizational skills, route modeling skills and possible non-standard situations, interactive teaching methods in preparation for the event, providing an active approach to education. Tourism is a means of self-improvement and self-realization of a person, a means of increasing physical activity and physical fitness of the young generation, a method of forming spiritual-ethical, social, professional and activity qualities that provide opportunities for self-realization in the interests of society and the individual.

As another example of the introduction of sports-health tourism to the physical education of students, we can cite his research, the basis of his innovative methodology of sports and health tourism is software, which includes: multi-day category trips, tourist multi-sport exercises, route exercises, sports rock climbing exercises, special including dynamic balance and vestibular stability exercises, water, hiking and ski tourism special preparation exercises.

The experience allows to achieve reliable positive changes in the psychological characteristics of students in indicators such as cooperation, competition, compromise, elimination and prevention of conflict situations, as well as in functional readiness of students in terms of PwC 170 indicators, Genche test, special dynamic balance, vestibular stability.

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